

ERIC Forum Implementation Project

Data Management Plan

Work Package 1 - Deliverable 1.5

Deliverable no	D1.5
Deliverable Title	Data Management Plan (DMP)
Contractual delivery month	6
Responsible Partner	Biobanking and BioMolecular Research Infrastructure – European Research Infrastructure Consortium (BBMRI-ERIC)
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Dissemination level	Public
Description of deliverable	The ERIC Forum DMP includes information on: - what data will be collected, processed and/or generated - which methodology & standards will be applied - whether data will be shared/made open access and - how data will be curated & preserved (including after the end of the project). The DMP will be produced in line with the FAIR principles (findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable), and with attention to the ethical requirements stated in Work Package 7 (WP7).

Executive summary

The DMP describes how information and data are collected/generated within the project.

As a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) the project does not produce research data. However, the project will collect personal data of project partners and key stakeholders, and project partners' contributions to the deliverables.

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Document log

Issue	Date (yyyy-mm-dd)	Comment	Author/partner
1	2020-04-07		Francesco Florindi, Viridiana Beltran Venegas, Ayodeji Adeniran
2	2020-07-22	Comments from WP leaders included	Francesco Florindi, Viridiana Beltran Venegas, Ayodeji Adeniran

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1. Data summary

Purpose of data collection and relation to project objectives

Data will be collected from project partners and stakeholders to fulfil the objectives of the projects, which are:

- Strengthening coordination and networking reinforcing the informal European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC) network or its successor framework;
- Support the organisation of specific meetings, targeted thematic workshops focusing on ERICs shared challenges such as the development of internal procurement rules, harmonized reporting, VAT exemption practices, insurances and pensions policies and training of governance bodies representatives;
- Support ERICs in preparation, based on best practices; and
- Support common communication and outreach activities and strengthening external representation of ERICs' as a stakeholder in consultations and other policy actions that could affect them.

Types and formats of data generated/collected

The project will collect:

- Limited personal information of the project participants and key stakeholders, including:
 - Name (s);
 - Email address (es);
 - Organisations they belong to;
 - Function within their organisations;
 - Interest in the project's activities;
- Best practices and experiences (reports, examples, interviews, etc) from the project partners and key stakeholders related to the creation, management and implementation of ERICs.

The project will generate:

- Reports, policy papers, best practices based on the information provided by the project partners and key stakeholders.

No existing data is being reused.

The data will originate directly from the project partners and the key stakeholders identified.

2. FAIR data

Data generated that are part of the project's deliverable, as per the Grant Agreement, will be made public via the project's website.

3. Allocation of resources

The project allocates 2 man/months to the project coordinator (BBMRI-ERIC) through the life of the project to set up and implement the DMP. The resources will be shared between:

- The Project Coordinator, Francesco Florindi, who is responsible for the daily coordination of the collection of data within the project;
- BBMRI-ERIC's Data Protection Officer (DPO), Ayodeji Adeniran, as DPO of the lead beneficiary to the project.

The DMP will be updated if needed. The Project Management Team (PMT) will assess the DMP periodically and propose edits if needed.

Long term preservation of the data collected will be extremely beneficial to the European research infrastructures ecosystem. After the project end, the cost of long-term preservation will be low (project's website domain, SharePoint license).

Because the project's data constitutes an important legacy for the whole ERIC Forum, the exact dispositions for how and where the data will be stored after the project will be discussed within the ERIC Forum General Assembly, in the last General Assembly of the project.

4. Data security

Backups

All data will be stored on the project online platform (SharePoint) that provides online backup. Physical backups will be created by the project officers at regular intervals. Backups will be stored by the project coordinator within the internal BBMRI-ERIC Servers. The Backups will be accessible only by the project coordinator. The backups will be stored for the duration of the project, and then passed on the Secretariat of the ERIC Forum, as legacy information linked to the activities of the Forum.

Right to access/correct/erase personal data

The right of users to access/correct/erase personal data will be ensured; with exception in certain circumstances:

- During the project: Users can contact the project coordinator at wp1@eric-forum.eu and request access/correction(s)/deletion of their personal data;
- After completion of the project: Users can contact the ERIC Forum Secretariat at secretariat@eric-forum.eu and request access/correction(s)/deletion of their personal data.

External participants within the project and who did not sign the Consortium Agreement will always be solicited for their consent and informed of the project's data protection policy when their data is being collected and processed. Likewise, their rights to access/correct/erase personal data will be ensured; with exception in certain circumstances.

5. Ethical aspects

The project foresees interviews and surveys. Participants will be properly informed, in writing, about the issues related to personal data protection and other aspects of participation in surveys/interviews, in compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (EU 2016/679) of the European Parliament and of the Council of April 27, 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data.